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EXPOSITION OF FOUR NOBLE TRUTHS IN YAMAKAPPAKARAṆA

Dr. Ramesh Prasad

Four Noble Truths are the basic principle of the Buddha's teachings. They are suffering (dukkha-saccain), origin of suffering (samudaya-saccam), cessation of suffering (nirodha-saccain) and a path leading to the cessation of suffering (magga-saccain). These truths, in the yamaka text of the Abhidhamma piṭaka, have not been discussed traditionally as disagreeable feeling of mind is suffering, desire is the cause of suffering, cessation of desire is the cessation of suffering and the eight fold path leads to the cessation of suffering, but have been analysed deeply and philosophically in abhidhammic way. The Sacca-Yamaka of the text discusses the fourfold truth in the form of different combinations of questions and answers that has been uniformly followed from beginning to end. The questions have been raised and attempts have been made to give their answers very minutely. The questions always appear in a dual form. Firstly the subject-matter has been discussed under three broad divisions, namely, Paṇṇattivāra, pavattivāra and pariññāvāra. Being a Vibhajjavādi the Buddha explains the dhammas by divisions so that they may be understood clearly. It is due to this reason the paṇṇattivāra and the pavattivāra have been classified. The paṇṇattivāra has two divisions, namely, Uddesa and Niddesa. In Uddesa the questions have been enumerated and in Niddesa these are in details. Both divisions have further been divided into two sections i.e. Anuloma and Paccaṇika. Anuloma has affirmative questions whereas Paccaṇika has questions in negative form-similarly pavattivāra has, further, been divided into three sections, viz. uppāḍavāra, Nirodhavāra and uppāda. Nirodhavāra. Each division has six groups. They are paccuppannavāra, atītavāra, anāgatavāra, paccuppannātītavāra, paccuppannānāgatavāra, and atītānāgatavāra. The questions under each group have been discussed with regard to person, place and both person and place.

PAṆṆATTIVĀRA

The literal meaning of the word 'Paṇṇatti' is designation. But it has been used here in technical sense, which means knowing the import and export of the term. There are many words which have, generally, been used to convey a particular technical sense. It is a fact that such words are the bearer of a particular meaning and used to denote that sense only. But, at the same time, it is also seen that a word changes its course of giving meaning in various contexts. The paṇṇattivāra has four sections, namely, padasodhanavāra,

padasodhanamūla cakkavāra, suddhasaccavāra and suddhasaccamūlacakkavāra. Under these heads the fourfold truth has been discussed. Here the questions on relation among the terms 'suffering' (dukkha), 'origin' (Samudaya), 'cessation' (nirodha) and 'path' (magga) and the respective terms for the four noble truths, between the general term 'truth' and the specific term for the four noble truths and between the terms 'truth' and 'suffering' etc. have been discussed.

Padasodhanavāra

The first question of the first pair follows as :

Dukkham dukkhasaccain ti ?¹

Whether suffering refers to the truth of suffering ?

We know that there are four truths. They are truth of suffering, origin of suffering, cessation of suffering and the path leading to the cessation of suffering. In this question the first truth is asked. Here we should clear first, what is suffering and what is truth of suffering ? The term suffering (dukkha) signifies the senses of bodily painful feeling (Kāyikaṃ dukkhaṃ) and mental painful feeling (cetasikaṃ dukkhaṃ) on the other hand, the truth of suffering (dukkha-sacca) does not merely refer to actual painful feeling (dukkha), but it also conveys that, on account of the law of impermanency and change, all the phenomena of existence are unsatisfactory and bear in themselves the seed of suffering and misery. Hence, it is obvious that suffering is the truth of suffering. Therefore, the answer Āmantā appears to be correct. It may be understood clearly by following diagram :

The second question of the pair proceeds as Dukkhasaccam dukkham ti ?²

Whether the truth of suffering is the suffering ?

The answer of this question is No. we have discussed in the first question that the truth of suffering covers many senses, such as kāyikaṃ dukkhaṃ, cetasikaṃ dukkhaṃ, etc. Avasesam dukkham is other than kāyikaṃ dukkhaṃ and cetasikaṃ dukkhaṃ. Therefore, answering this question it may be said that except bodily and mental painful feeling the remaining truth of suffering is

dukkha-sacca, but it is not dukkha.

Bodily and mental painful feeling, however, is painful feeling (dukkha) as well as truth of suffering (dukkha-sacca). The text answers it with following words :

Kāyikaṃ dukkhaṃ cetasikaṃ dukkhaṃ ṭhapetvā avasesaṃ dukkhasaccaṃ, na dukkhaṃ. Kāyikaṃ dukkhaṃ cetasikaṃ dukkhaṃ dukkhaṃ ceva dukkhasaccaṃ ca.³

For clear understanding following diagram may be presented :

Similarly, other three truths have been discussed in the text. The same questions have also been discussed in the negative form. For example :

Na dukkhaṃ na dukkhasaccaṃ ti ? Kāyikaṃ dukkhaṃ cetasikaṃ dukkhaṃ ṭhapetvā avasesā na dukkhaṃ, dukkhasaccaṃ. Dukkhaṃ ca dukkhasaccaṃ ca ṭhapetvā avasesaṃ na ceva dukkhaṃ na ca dukkhasaccaṃ.⁴

The second question of this pair follows as :

Na dukkhasaccaṃ na dukkhaṃ ti ?⁵

Āmantā.

The explanation of this pair is similar to that of the first pair of the Padasodhanavāra. We have already explained that dukkhasaccaṃ covers not only dukkhaṃ but also remaining dukkhasaccaṃ. Therefore, in answer of the first question it may be said that excepting bodily and mental painful feeling other truth of suffering covers dukkhasaccaṃ. Therefore, it cannot be said that these dhammas which are not suffering are also not the truth of suffering. The second question is reverse to the first. When there is devoid of truth of suffering how the dhamma like dukkha can exist. The presence of dukkha depends on the presence of dukkhasacca. Therefore, the answer Āmantā appears to be correct.

Padasodhanamūlacakkavāra

The first pair of this vāra follows as :

Dukkhaṃ dukkhasaccaṃ ti ?
& saccā samudayasaccaṃ ti ?⁶

Whether suffering refers to the truth of suffering ? & whether truths refer to the truth & origin of suffering ? The first question has been discussed in the padasodhanavāra. Here we should discuss the second question. We know that there are four truths, namely, Dukkhaṃ, Samudayaṃ, Nirodhaṃ and Maggaṃ. It is obvious that samudaya-saccaṃ is one of the four saccas. Hence, answering this question it may be said that samudayasaccaṃ refers to both saccam and samudayasaccaṃ. But Avasesā saccā i.e. Dukkhaṃ, Nirodhaṃ and Maggaṃ do not refer to samudayasacca. The text answers this question as :

Samudayasaccaṃ saccam ceva samudayasaccaṃ ca. Avasesā saccā na samudayasaccaṃ.⁷

It may be clearly understood by following diagram :

Suddhasaccavāra

The first pair of the suddhasaccavāra runs as :

Dukkhaṃ Saccam ti ?
& Saccā dukkhasaccaṃ ti ?⁸

Whether suffering refers to truth ?
& whether truths refer to the truth of suffering ?

We have discussed fourfold truth. Among these four truths dukkha is the first truth. Therefore, the answer āmantā of the first question appears to be correct.

The explanation of the second question is also the same as that of the second question of the padasodhanamūlacakkavāra. Answering this question it may be said that truth of suffering is both truth and truth of suffering. Remaining truths i.e. truth of origination, truth of cessation and truth of path, however, are not truth of suffering, but are the truths.

Suddhasaccamūlacakkavāra

In this section also there are pairs of questions. But the questions mentioned under this section are not new. They have already been enumerated in previous

sections i.e. Padasodhanavāra, Padasodhanamūlacakkavāra and Suddhasaccavāra. Here, attempts have been made to collect all possible pairs of questions. Questions are not new here but the pairs of these questions are new. For instance, we may take the first pair of this section :

Dukkhaṃ Saccam ti ?

& Saccā Samudayasaccam ti ?⁹

whether suffering is truth ?

& whether truths are the truth of origination

The first question is available in suddhasaccavāra, while the second question has been enumerated in the Padasodhanamūlacakkavāra.

PAVATTIVĀRA

The word 'Pavatti' as it literally indicates, is starting, beginning, to remain in tune with the idea, but here it has been used in the sense of process. It conveys three senses, namely, uppādavāra, nirodhavāra and uppādanirodhavāra.

Uppādavāra

Excepting the truth of cessation (Nibbāna) this section explains the arising of remaining three truths of suffering, as no arising and ceasing of the same is possible at a moment. [The truth of suffering arises at the moment consciousness unconnected with craving (tanhāvippayuttacitta) arises in those who undergo rebirth, but the truth of origin does not arise then. At the moment craving arises, both truths arise. Similarly, the truth of suffering, and not the truth of the path, arises when consciousness is not connected with the path; when consciousness is so connected, both truths arise. In the immaterial world (arūpa) only the truth of the path arises; among the unconscious beings, only the truth of suffering; among beings in the lower world (apāya), only the truths of suffering and origin; but among beings with five aggregates all the three truths arise.] For clear understanding some questions of the text may be explained. The first question of the vāra follows as :

Yassa dukkhasaccam uppajjati tassa

samudayasaccam uppajjati ?¹⁰

whether the person whose truth of suffering

arises, the truth of origin also arises to him ?

We have discussed four truths in earlier pages, namely, truth of suffering, truth of origination, truth of cessation and truth of the path. Have the questions have been asked in the light of truth of suffering and truth of origination. Answering this question it may be said that to those persons, who are being reborn, in the course of existence, there arises the truth of suffering at the moment of arising of consciousness disconnected with craving (tanhāvippayuttacitta), but at the moment the truth of origination does not arise. It happens because of the fact that suffering may arise without craving. As we know that 'dukkha-sahagataṃ kāyaviññānaṃ' is one of the akusala-ahetuka-citta. In this case one feels suffering without attaching craving. But in

taṇhāvippayuttacitta case, there does not arise truth of origination. Whenever truth of origination exists, there must be the existence of craving, without craving truth of origination cannot exist. On the other hand at the appearance of craving both truths, the truth of suffering and the truth of origination arise. The text explains this question as :

Sabbesaṃ upapajjantānaṃ pavatte taṇhā-vippayuttacittassa uppādakkhaṇe tesāṃ dukkhasaccaṃ uppajjati, no ca tesāṃ samudayasaccaṃ uppajjati. Taṇhāya uppādakkhaṇe tesāṃ dukkhasaccaṃ ca uppajjati samudayasaccaṃ ca uppajjati.¹¹

To all those, who are being reborn, arises, in the course of existence, at the moment of arising of consciousness disconnected with craving, the dukkha-truth but not the samudaya-truth; at the appearance of craving, however, both do arise, the truth of suffering as well as the truth of origination. The second question of the pair proceeds as :

Yassa vā pana samudayasaccaṃ uppajjati
tassa dukkhasaccaṃ uppajjati ti ?¹²

Whether the person whose truth of origination arises, the truth of suffering also arises to him ?

We know that craving is the cause of origin of suffering. Wherever cause is present, there effect exists also. Existence of the truth of origination means the existence of craving and the existence of craving shows the existence of suffering. It is due to this reason, it is said that the persons whose truth of origination arises, the truth of suffering also arises to him. Therefore, the answer āmantā appears to be correct.

The questions related to samudayasaccaṃ and maggasaccaṃ may also be discussed. The pair of questions regarding the truth of origination and the truth of path follows as :

Yassa samudayasaccaṃ uppajjati tassa maggasaccaṃ uppajjati ti ?
& Yassa vā pana maggasaccaṃ uppajjati tassa samudayasaccaṃ uppajjati ti ?¹³

Whether the person/whose truth of origination arises, the truth of path of the same person also arises ?

& Whether the person whose truth of path arises, the truth of origination of that person also arises ?

Both questions have negative answers. Samudayasaccaṃ denotes the sense of cause of arising of suffering and maggasaccaṃ conveys about the path i.e. the eightfold path. We know that the desire or craving is the cause of suffering and this suffering can be stopped by following eightfold path i.e. right view, right resolution, right speech, right action, right livelihood, right effort, right mindfulness and right concentration. Now the question arises, when origination of suffering arises, then whether the path to the cessation of suffering arises or not ? The answer is no because origination of suffering

does not lead to its cessation. When one wants to eradicate suffering then he follows the path and gradually he becomes free from suffering. Therefore, it can be said that the persons whose truth of origination arises, the truth of path of the same person does not arise and vice-versa.

Nirodhavāra

In this vāra cessation of the truth has been discussed. The first question of this section follows as :

Yassa dukkhasaccam nirujjhati tassa samudaya-saccam nirujjhatiti ?¹⁴

Whether the person whose truth of suffering ceases, the truth of origination also ceases to him ?

The person whose truth of suffering ceases, the truth of origination of the same person may cease or may not cease. It depends on the context. When a person is dying at the moment of ceasing of consciousness disconnected with craving, the truth of suffering ceases, but not the origination-truth. However, at the moment of ceasing of craving both truths i.e. truth of suffering and truth of origination cease. The text explains it with following words :

Sabbesam cavantānam pavatte taṇhāvippayutta-cittassa bhaṅgakkhaṇe tesam dukkhasaccam nirujjhati, no ca tesam samudayasaccam nirujjhati. Taṇhāya bhaṅgakkhaṇe tesam dukkhasaccam ca nirujjhati samudayasaccam ca nirujjhati.¹⁵

The second question of the pair proceeds as :

Yassa vā pana samudayasaccam nirujjhati tassa dukkhasaccam nirujjhatī ti ?¹⁶

Whether the person whose truth of origination ceases, the truth of suffering also ceases to him ?

We have discussed in previous pages that craving is the cause of origin of suffering. When craving is annihilated, there is no suffering at all. Therefore, the answer āmantā seems to be correct.

Similarly, other pairs of questions have been discussed.

Uppāda-Nirodhavāra

The uppāda-nirodhavāra discusses the questions on the arising and ceasing of the truths. The question enquires whether the arising of one truth and the ceasing of the another truth are possible at the same moment. For clear understanding we discuss following pair :

Yassa dukkhasaccam uppajjati tassa samudaya-saccam nirujjhatī ti ?
& Yassa vā pana samudayasaccam nirujjhati tassa dukkhasaccam uppajjati ti ?¹⁷

Whether the person whose truth of suffering arises, the truth of origination of the same person ceases ?

& whether the person whose truth of origination ceases, the truth of suffering of the same person arises ?

The answer of both questions is in negative. In the first question there are two aspects. The first aspect is the person whose truth of suffering arises. It means that there is desire which arises suffering. The second aspect deals with the ceasing of the truth of origination. The first aspect and the second aspect cannot exist at the same time because arising of the truth of suffering is due to the truth of origination. Then how we can say that the person whose truth of suffering arises, the truth of origination of the same person ceases. Therefore, the answer 'No' seems to be right. The similar reason is also applied for the second question of the pair.

PARIÑÑĀVĀRA

The Pariññāvāra explains about insight of the four noble truths. One fully understands truths after developing insight. Here also the questions have been asked in affirmation as well as in negation. The same questions have been asked in present tense, past tense, future tense and in the combinations of present-past, present-future and past-future as asked in the pavattivāra. Some questions may be discussed for clear understanding. The first question of the first pair follows as :

Yo dukkhasaccam parijānāti so samudayasaccam pajahatī ti?¹⁸

Whether someone who fully understands the truth of suffering, also overcomes the truth of origination ?

A Yogāvacara gets Nibbāna after destroying his defilements. His consciousness becomes now very subtle and in this state he understands the things as they are, not as they appear to be. He fully understands the fourfold truth. Comprehending truths he overcomes desires which are cause of origin of suffering. Therefore, it may be said that a man, who penetrates the truth of suffering, overcomes the truth of origination. It is due to this reason the text has answered the question in affirmation.

The second question of the first pair proceeds as :

Yo vā pana samudayasaccam pajahati

So dukkhasaccam parijānāti ti?¹⁹

Whether the person who overcomes the truth of origination, fully understands the truth of suffering ?

This question has also got affirmative answer. A person who abandons desires, is called an Arahata. An arahata, after putting off desires, penetrates the fourfold truth. Hence, it may be said here that someone who overcomes desires, penetrates the truth of suffering. Therefore, the answer āmantā appears to be correct.

Similarly, other pairs of questions have also been discussed.

It is in this way the four noble truths have been explained in the catechetical method in the yamakappakarāṇa very nicely.

NOTES AND REFERENCES

1. Yamaka I, p. 315 (Nalanda edition).
2. *Ibid.*
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4. Yamaka I, p. 316.
5. *Ibid.*
6. Yamaka I, p. 317.
7. *Ibid.*
8. Yamaka I, p. 320.
9. Yamaka I, p. 321.
10. Yamaka I, p. 323.
11. *Ibid.*
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14. Yamaka I, p. 355.
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16. *Ibid.*
17. Yamaka I, p. 382.
18. Yamaka I, p. 397.
19. *Ibid.*